

Capital Structure and Financial Performance of Quoted Telecommunication Companies in Nigeria

ADEJUWON Joshua Adewale¹, LASISI Abisola Mutiat² and ADEJUWON
Adefisayo Oluwakemi³

^{1,2,3}Department of Management and Accounting, Lead City University, Ibadan,
Nigeria;

¹adejuwon.joshua@lcu.edu.ng || +234 803 371 5590

²2abisolamutiat946@gmail.com; +2348142438592

³adejuwonoluwakemi218@gmail.com; +2347063693491

Abstract

Capital structure is a mixture of the financing options a company uses to finance its investments. However, deciding on an optimal capital mix has been a huge task for most telecommunication companies. The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of capital structure on performance of the quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria. The study used an *ex-post facto* research design. The study population consisted of 9 quoted telecommunication companies on Nigeria Stock exchange. The purposive sampling technique was adopted to select a sample of seven (7) telecommunication firms for the period of ten years (2012-2021). Data for this study were extracted from the published annual reports and accounts of the sampled companies and validated by the statutory auditors. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that short term debt, long term debt, equity and total debt had joint and significant effect on profit before tax, return on asset, return on equity and return on capital employed of quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria. (PBT – *Adj. R*² = 0.8034, *Wald test* = 71.51 *p* < 0.05; ROA – *Adj. R*² = 0.1543, *Wald test* = 4.15, *p* < 0.05). The study concluded that capital structure had significant effects on the performance of telecommunication companies in Nigeria. It was recommended that the management of the telecommunication companies should pay attention to the composition of capital structure in term of short term debt, long term debt, equity and total debt and should be careful and cautious in accumulating debt that could eventually have adverse effects on their value and financial performance.

Keywords: Capital structure, Performance, Profit before tax, Return on asset, Return on equity

Word count: 279

Introduction

Continuous existence of any company depend mainly on makeup or capital structure of the company (Andrew, Ademola & Adetayo, 2021). This is so because performance of company either financial or otherwise dependent on the composition of capital structure. Company fully financed by equity will yield a return different from that financed by debt, while performance of those with mixture will be different (Yinusa, Ismail, Yulia & Olawale, 2019). Investors considered structure of capital as very vital before investing in the company because of its effect on performance. The capital structure of a firm is a combination of the various sources through which a firm is financed (El-Maude, Ahmad & Ahmad, 2016). Risk and reward associated with capital structure make it one of the most difficult decisions that business managers made. The capital structure of a company is made up of equity, debt, and debt with preferred stock; this combination is referred to as the long-term financing mix of the company (El-Maude, Ahmad & Ahmad, 2016).

Capital structure decision is fundamental for the conscious existence of any business because it is necessary to maximize returns for the many stakeholders involved and because it has a significant impact on a company's capacity to operate in a market that is highly competitive (Yinusa, Ismail, Yulia & Olawale, 2019). Consequently, any decision made by the financial managers with regards to the funding of its operation could affect the business's positively or negatively. Also, need to maximize return on investment and competitive environment in which business operate nowadays has make capital structure decision to be very essential to all business stakeholders. In addition, capital structure decision impact directly on the financial standing and firm's stability. Effectiveness of firm usage of its resources with the aim of improving profitability rest on financial manager decision on the structure of capital in place (Yinusa, Ismail, Yulia & Olawale, 2019).

The modern capital structure theory by Modigliani and Miller states that, under the ideal capital market hypothesis, the association's esteem is autonomous with the construction of capital. Every business organization view capital structure decision to be very essential and are never taking with levity as it can affect going concern of an entity. It is a top management decision as it affect firms value (Abu-Rub, 2012). Maximization of firm value is the main concern why firm chose a balance debt portfolio by using right mixture of debt

and equity. Also, a poor judgment by financial manager of a company in selecting the right mix of debt and equity could result in financial failure and may lead to bankruptcy eventually (Vu, Le & Nguyen, 2020)

The financial decision of a company is important in determining the optimal capital structure mix (Andrew, Ademola & Adetayo, 2021). Firms use a variety of levels of leverage; however, corporate finance theory and financial literature have yet to identify the ideal combination for managers to use in order to improve performance (Chung, Yang & Won 2018). Long-term debt, short-term debt, common equity, preferred equity, and retained earnings make up the capital structure (Andrew, Ademola & Adetayo, 2021). The ability of a company to maximize shareholder value and wealth and to earn the highest possible returns on its assets is what determines how successful it is (El-Maude, Ahmad & Ahmad 2016). Depending on the risk level associated with each financing choice as well as the correlation between risk and return, businesses will choose different types of financing (Yinusa, Ismail, Yulia & Olawale, 2019).

Lot of factors such as profitability, growth of the firm, firm size, maturity of debt, debt ratio, tax and tangibility need to be considered before capital structure decision is taken. However, lot of researchers has focused attention on major considerations affecting the capital structure decisions in the light of risk level of a firm. A firm's capital structure must be developed with emphases on risk because it has a direct link with the value (Sorana, 2015).

Researchers has been concern with the effect of capital structure on financial performance of companies. Outcome of their study is still not conclusive as result has been conflicting most especially when compare outcome of developed nation to that of developing nations Companies in Nigeria are faced with critical financing decisions on the optimal capital structure that will be suitable for the organization and such financing decisions are important to the profitability of the firm (Vu, Le & Nguyen'2020)

Determination of optimal capital structure of companies in Nigeria has become so critical, widening and deepening as it affect market rating of firms (Chung, Yang & Won, 2018). Corporate sector is characterized by a large number of firms operating in a largely deregulated and increasingly competitive environment (Chung, Yang & Won, 2018) Business operating environment of firms has changed tremendously since 1987, when business and financial environment has been liberalized (Chung, Yang & Won, 2018). This study examined the effect of capital structure on financial performance of the quoted

telecommunication companies in Nigeria. However, the specific objectives were set to:

- i. establish the extent to which capital structure affects profit before tax of quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria.
- ii. determine the effect of capital structure on return on asset of quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Concept of Financial Performance

Financial performance principally reflects business sector outcomes and results that shows overall financial health of the sector over a specific period of time. It indicates how well an entity is utilizing its resources to maximize the shareholder's wealth and profitability (Farah, Farrukh & Faizaan, 2016). Although a complete evaluation of a firm's financial performance takes into account many other different kinds of measures but most common performance measurement used in the field of finance and statistical inference is financial ratios (Muhammad, Bujang & Hakim, 2019).

The financial performance of a company is significant to shareholders, investors, and the stakeholder large. The returns on their investments are what interest investors (Mirza & Javed 2013). A firm that is performing well can reward its investors more favorably by paying high divided and or high share value, however it is commonly known that a company that is not performing well cannot draw informed investor (Onyebuchi 2020) On the other hand, a company's performance can be viewed as the outcome of how effectively it evaluated its own performance or strategy in achieving its goals and objectives (Gong, Arugu & Dandago, 2014). An indicator of a company's ability to effectively employ resources from business operations to generate revenue is financial performance.

The performance of a firm reflects how effectively the firm has been managed and resources utilized (Muhammad, Bujang & Hakim, 2019)

Performance Measurement

Different measures have been adopted in the literature to measure organizational performance. This study will use accounting based method as it is easily extracted from the financial reports of the company which is available in the public domain. Many researchers

have made use of the accounting base measures of performance in their various study successfully (Haron 2014). Past researcher has considered Accounting based measurement as a good gauge of the company's performance in term of profitability (Houshang, Suzan, Mustafa, Nawaz & Rezart, 2022). The accounting based measurement indicators to the profitability of firms on the short term in the past years are: Return on assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Return on Investment (ROI), Profit Margin (PM), Earnings per share (EPS), Operation Profit (OP), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE), Expense to Assets (ETA), Sales to assets STS) and others. The following measurement shall be explained as it is used in this study.

Return on Equity (ROE)

Return on Equity (ROE) is measured by profit after tax over total equity shares in issue (Ogebe& Alewi 2013). It is a financial ratio that tells you how much net income a company generates per naira of invested capital. This percentage is key because it helps investors understand how efficiently and effectively a firm uses its capital to generate profit (Opoku-Asante, Winful, Sharifzadeh & Neubert 2022). Study conducted in this area revealed existence of significant relationship between the Return on Equity and the performance of companies listed in the Abu Dhabi Securities Exchange (Cheng, 2019).

Return on Asset (ROA)

The term Return On Asset refers to a financial ratio that indicates how profitable a company is in relation to its total assets (Khazaaleh 2017). It measured level of profitability in relation to total asset of the company. Analysts, investors and other company's stakeholders used ROA to determine how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate a profit (Narinder & Mahima 2019).

Profit before Taxation: Profit before tax is a measure that looks at a company's profits before the company has to pay corporate income tax (Owolabi, Kolawole, Ogungbade & Adekoya 2021). It is all company's profits without the consideration of any taxes. Profit before tax can be found on the income statement as operating profit minus interest. Profit before tax is the value used to calculate a company's tax obligation (Haron, 2014).

Capital Structure: Capital structure is the composition of the capital employed by the firm from various sources of finance. It comprises of both owners capital (i.e. equity capital and preferred capital) and debt capital. The capital structure of the firm represents its investment and financing strategy (Abbas, Aziz. & Khan, 2018). Entity capital structure mean combination of various form in which a firm is financing. Financing open to firm is

combination of long term and short term sources (Owolabi, Kolawole, Ogungbade & Adekoya, 2021)

Capital structure as an arrangement of the different components of business funds, i.e. shareholder's funds and borrowed funds in proper proportion (Musila, 2015). The capital structure of a company is made up of both its financial liabilities and its equity. It is the process through which a business finances its assets using a mix of equity and debt (Myers & Majluf 1984). Accordingly, it is referred to as a combination of several instruments (long-term debt, common stock) that a company issues to finance its assets. It can also be referred to as the ratios of different types of capital employed in a business, such as equity capital and debt capital, each of which has advantages and disadvantages of its own (Saad, Abdul-Ghani, Ahmad & Salim, 2021). From the aforementioned, it can be seen that a company's capital structure is simply its financial framework, which consists of retained earnings, debt financing, and equity financing to keep the business entity in operation (Arthur, 2019). The two primary capital structure classes are debt and equity. The two types of debt are short-term and long-term (Achieng, Muturi & Wanjare, 2019). These elements are frequently discussed as equity and total asset ratios in accounting and finance literature. The elements are mentioned below.

Components of Capital Structure

The capital structure of the company is nothing but taking decision-related to the acquisition of funds from various sources and composition of debts and equity. Followings are the multiple sources of funds which the company takes into consideration while determining its capital structure: There are many theories that explain how investors can build the best capital structure, which improves the firm's market value by selecting the best mixture of equity financing and debt financing and theories on capital structure (Arthur, 2019). Various studies have been conducted on the capital structure in developed countries and a few have been performed in developing countries. Logically, most of the authors have found a positive relationship while others have found a negative association between capital structure and firm performance (Olusola, Mengze, Muruako & Agulefo, 2022).

In developed countries, it is well said that most wall street analyst and investors tend to focus on Return on equity (ROE) as their primary measure of company performance, even though more sophisticated valuation techniques like internal rate of return (IRR), cash flow return on investments (CFRI), Discounted cash flow analysis (DCF) have come along (Ogieva & Ogiemudia, 2019). They also stated the return on assets (ROA) a better metric of

financial performance, than income statement profitability measures like return on sales (ROS). No single metric is perfect and different metrics are appropriate depending upon the circumstances as categorized in the measurements of performance which is divided into two: Accounting based measurement and marketing based measurement (Johnny & Ayunku, 2019)

Equity Financing

Equity financing is the process of raising capital through the sale of shares. Equity financing carries no repayment obligation and provides extra working capital that can be used to grow a business. Thus, it is a method of raising fresh capital by selling shares of the company to public, institutional investors, or financial institutions. The people who buy shares are referred to as shareholders of the company because they have received ownership interest in the company. Equity financing is an integral component of the capital structure of the firm apart from debts³⁸. The relatively low level of risk related to equity financing as opposed to debt financing has resulted into an increased recognition and use of equities in financing investment projects in organizations (Orji, Nwadiolor & Agubata, 2021).

To know ratio of borrowing out of the total capital of a company total debt (including current liabilities) is always divided by the equity held by its shareholders¹¹. In order to increase the amount of a company's funding provided by shareholders and to increase the cushion (margin of protection) in the case of declining asset prices or outright losses, creditors prefer that this ratio be lower. Total debt to total equity is defined as the ratio of a company's total liabilities to its total shareholder equity (Basit & Hassan, 2017). This contrasts the promises made by shareholders with those of suppliers, lenders, creditors, etc. Numerous empirical research carried out in Nigeria and other countries have demonstrated that a company's total debt to total equity ratio is anticipated to have a substantial impact on a firm's financial performance (Cheng, 2019).

Short Term Debt: Short-term debt refers to items where the repayment period is lesser than twelve months such as account payables, accruals (Muhammad, Bujang & Hakim, 2019) It gauges how much of a firm's total short-term debt is expected to be repaid during an accounting period. The short-term debt to total assets ratio was calculated (Ayange, Nwude, Idamoyibo Hwerien & Ufodiama, 2021). Some argue that a company's performance will improve if its debt is kept to a minimum (Olusola, Mengze, Muruako, & Agulefo, 2022). Others, however, believe that short-term debt can be expensive because it must be repaid in a hurry, which eventually affects the company's ability to manage its cash

flow (Ogieva & Ogiemudia ,2019). It was equally empirically showed that short term debt influenced financial performance negatively and significantly (Johnny & Ayunku, 2019) According to a study on the relationship between short-term debt and a company's performance, the ratio of short-term debt to total assets considerably hurts financial performance Ibrahim, (2019). Furthermore, a further investigation examining the relationship between capital structure and firm performance found that there is only a weak correlation between short-term debt to total assets and firm financial performance (Mouna, Jianmu, Havidz & Ali, 2017).

Long-term Debt

The long-term debt financing is a measurement representing the percentage of a company's assets financed with long-term debt. This includes loans or other form of debt obligations lasting more than one year (Achieng, Muturi & Wanjare, 2019). This ratio provides a general measure of the long-term financial position of a company, including its ability to meet its financial obligations for outstanding loans. If a company recorded a consistent year-over year decrease in a company's long-term debt-to-total-assets ratio may indicate that it is becoming progressively less dependent on debt to grow its business (Rahman & Uddin, 2019).

Study on effect of long term financing and performance have revealed mixed result, while some argues that the higher the long-term debt to total assets the greater the return on assets. Other study claimed that the ratio of long-term debt to total assets and financial success is significantly inverse (Saad, Abdul-Ghani, Ahmad & Salim, 2020). It was argued that long term financing has many benefits such as lower financing costs, it is mostly structured and stable over time (Pinto, Hawaldar, Quadras & Joseph, 2017) It was discussed that firms' ability to obtain long-term financing tends to be greater in countries with a contestable, well-regulated banking system and with developed capital markets (Birru, 2016). Weakness in the contractual environment is an important underlying reason why long-term debt is less common in developing countries (Evbayiro-Osagie & Enadeghe, 2022). When lenders cannot rely on legal institutions to enforce their claims to loan repayment, they may prefer to lend short term, so that the continued need for renegotiation provides incentives for borrowers to exert effort and make sound investments (Myers & Majluf, 1984.)

Despite the fact that long term debt can be used to increase shareholder return, it can also cause agency problems. Firms tend to match the maturity of their assets and liabilities, and thus they often use long-term debt to make long-term investments, such as purchases of

fixed assets or equipment. Long-term finance also offers protection from credit supply shocks and having to refinance in bad times. However, the theoretical literature is inconclusive on how the maturity structure of debt financing affects firm performance most especially in telecommunication sector. On the one hand, long-term debt finance is likely to have a positive effect on investment and performance for firms that need it since it allows firms to invest in projects that bring in returns in a relatively long time. On the other hand, long-term finance can distort managers' incentives, hampering investment and firm performance. Thus, the existence of a link between a firm's long term debt financing and financial performance though has been a hotly debated area of accounting research, the results are still mixed (Ogebe & Alewi, 2015).

Optimal Capital Structure

The best combination of debt and equity financing for a company's capital structure optimizes market value while lowering cost of capital. Theoretically, because debt financing is tax deductible, it has the lowest cost of capital. However, if debt levels are too high, shareholders will face greater financial risk and will need a higher return on equity. Therefore, businesses must determine the ideal point at which the marginal advantage of borrowing money balances out the marginal cost (Nassar, 2021). The key features of optimum capital structure are its simplicity and ability to ensure maximum profitability by minimizing the cost of capital. It works on the aspects of control, conservatism, flexibility, and a regulated debt-equity mix. A company's optimal capital structure is important for several reasons. In many cases, it can help a company save money on its financing costs. If a company has a lower debt-to-equity ratio, it will often have a lower cost of capital because equity is typically less expensive to finance than debt. Additionally, an optimal capital structure can help a company reduce business risks, such as the risk of bankruptcy. An optimal capital structure can help a company maximize its market value, improve its financial flexibility, and attract and retain investors (Opoku-Asante, Winful, Sharifzadeh & Neubert, 2022)

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Agency theory. Agency theory is one of the theory used to predict the optimal structure in past literature (Okolo, Okwu, Ugwuoke & Kornom-Gbaraba, 2019). Since shareholders are separated from the management of businesses, an agency relationship is created. This also creates a conflict of interest situation called the agency problem. According to the agency problem, whilst managers seek their own best interest, shareholders will be expecting them to work towards maximizing the value of their investment (gong, Arugu & Dandago, 2014). We find that these opposing interests can

eventually lead to situations that predicts the optimal capital structure. The agency problem leads to indiscriminate expenditure by managers who have enough cash at their disposal (Ganiyu, Adelopo, Rodionova & Olawale, 2019). This was supported by prior researcher where it was stated that, the agency problem is created because management may have enough cash to spend on their pet projects rather than on value maximizing projects (Haron, 2014). For instance, managers with excess cash may spend them on things like flashy offices, corporate jets, and things of that nature which does little to maximize shareholder's wealth (Abdikadir, 2015).

On the other hand, managers with very little cash are not in the position to be that wasteful. The central issues in agency theory are therefore how to resolve the fight for the control of firm resources between managers and shareholders. Some theories have suggested a strategy of increasing the use of debt capital in order to reduce the agency cost problem. Other study concluded that, agency issues may have led SMEs to pursue high debt policies leading to lower performance (Abdullah & Tursoy, 2021)`. The reason for this is that, the risk of financial distress from increasing the use of debt may encourage managers to reduce wasteful spending. Agency problem suggests the use of debt contracts as the main means of transferring wealth to investors. This may be because, it deters wasteful spending, and therefore increasing amounts available to shareholders (Akinleye & Akomolafe, 2019). Also, the use of debt makes wasteful management focus on debt repayments in order to avoid bankruptcy from the inability to pay. The survival of the business therefore becomes a big concern for managers (Akinleye & Akomolafe, 2019). **Empirical Review**

This section offers some understanding of earlier studies on the capital structure and financial performance of telecommunications companies conducted by various scholars in various nations at various times. Results of earlier study in this area are described below:

Farah, Farrukh and Faizaan, (2016) conducted research in India, on the impact of capital structure on the profitability of 50 companies listed on the National Stock Exchange of India between 2008 to 2017. The data was analyzed using multiple panel data regression models, descriptive statistics, and correlation. Four different regression models were employed to evaluate the relationship between capital structure and profitability. It was discovered that a firm's capital structure had a significant positive impact on its profitability`

Patel, Borde, Mistry and Purohit, (2020) investigated in USA on the effect of capital structure on firms' profitability of telecommunication companies. Annual data of the telecom industry from 2012 to 2020 in the USA, comprising 421 firm-year observations for

72 firms were studied using pooled panel regression, univariate analysis, correlation, and descriptive statistics models. Impact of Capital Structure was tested using Total Liabilities to Total Assets and Total Equity to Total Assets on the profitability using Return on Assets and Return on Equity of firms in the telecommunication industry in the USA. The results reveal that the ratio of Total Liabilities to Total Assets has a significant impact on Return On Asset, and Total Equity to Total Assets has a significant impact on ROA.

Mirza and Javed, (2013) carried out in Malaysia on the relationship between the source of capital via equity and debt financing, and the performance of small and medium enterprise revealed that SMEs in Malaysia employ equity financing as a source of business capital, for its potential (capability) in affecting the performance of business. The study is run based on of postal survey using cluster sampling method. It comprises of 177 samples of Malaysian SMEs involving in manufacturing and agriculture sectors. Subsequently, two research hypotheses are developed and analyzed. It is found that equity financing has significant positive relationship on the business performance, while debt financing is insignificant. The study suggests that SMEs in Malaysia to employ equity financing as a source of business capital, for its potential (capability) in affecting the performance of business

Onyebuchi, (2020) examined on the impact of capital structure on the competitiveness of the manufacturing industry in Ghana. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Outcome of the study revealed that short term debt and long term debt had a negative effect on productivity and on the contrary equity has a positive relationship with profitability.

Musila, (2015) Similar to the above study was conducted to evaluates the effects of debt and equity financing on corporate performance among the Chinese listed firms' revealing that capital structure have significantly negative consequence on corporate performance. Hence, the study shows that it is risky for companies to depend entirely on either debt or equity for raising capital but it is far better to raise capital by both methods, with each employed together, at the same time. This method is better as it affords the benefit of one method offsetting the problems of the other and vice versa

Ibrahim, (2019) investigation conducted in Pakistan on the impact of debt financing on airline's (transport) sector performance revealed that that there is opposite relationship between debt financing and financial performance of airlines. Debt is measured from three ratios, short term debt to total assets, long term debt to total assets and total debt to total assets ratio. For the measurement of performance, return on assets and earnings per share

were used. Data from secondary sources. In this study, we used a data sample of 11 years from 2008-2018 by using companies' annual reports. Due to unavailability of data, only 3 transport companies have been taken for analysis. The software which we used in analysis is SPSS. It was concluded on the basis of findings that the companies should focus on retained earnings which is cheaper source of finance and use less level of debt. As the more level of debt use by the companies, the performance of companies' decrease.

Muhammad, Bujang and Hakim, (2019) study revealed that capital structure decisions are among the most important and crucial decisions for any business because of their effect on the firm's value. Impact of capital structure of banks in Ethiopia on financial performance where study for a period of five (5) years between 2011 to 2015. Data was analyzed using quantitative approach of multiple regression models. The study used return on equity and return on assets to measure performance as dependent variable and capital structure was measured using debt ratio, debt to equity ratio, loan to deposit, bank's size and asset tangibility as independent variable. The results reveals that financial performance is significantly and negatively associated with capital structure. Conclusion drawn from the study was that the capital structure proxies have impact on financial performance of commercial bank. From the findings, it is strongly recommended that firms should focus on the proportion of debt used by the bank, the manner of utilizing the resources while expanding the banks and the amount of investment on fixed asset.

Haron (2014) examined the effect of capital structure on the return-on-assets (ROA) performance of non-financial enterprises over a nine-year period (2012-2020). The capital structure variables of long term debt to equity (LTDQ), total debt (TD), total debt to equity (TDQ), and total debt to total assets (TDTA), as well as the ROA performance, were examined for a total of forty (40) non-financial enterprises. The approach of panel data analysis was used. All factors were significant at the 1% level, and it was discovered that LTDQ, TD, and TDQ have favorable effects on ROA performance while TDTA has a negative effect. The study recommends that, since long term debt to equity strongly explain corporate performance in the Sub-Saharan African Countries, management should sustain their current policies and should also be very sensitive in determining the appropriate amount of long term debt that ought to be included in their capital structure build up.

Meshack, Owa, Nwadiolor and Chiedu, (2022) study conducted in Nigeria on the effect of Debt Equity Financing on Performance of quoted Firms in Nigeria revealed that Debt Equity Financing has significant and positive effect on Firms Performance. Debt equity financing was proxy using the variables of equity financing and debt equity financing

while Firms Performance on the other hand was measured using Return on equity. Data for the study were gathered from the Nigeria Exchange Group Fact Book, Annual Reports, and Accounts using the Ex Post Facto design of research. The study's conclusions showed that debt equity financing significantly and favorably affects firms' performance in Nigeria. According to the study's findings, debt-equity financing enhances a firm's performance over time. It was advised that firms try to finance their investment operations with debts and equity and only consider debt or equity as a last resort¹⁴ based on the study's findings. Abdikadir, (2015) examined the relationship between capital structure and financial performance and took into consideration the impact of loan maturity using 425 cross-sectional firm-year samples from companies in Ghana and Nigeria. According to the empirical findings, there is a significant inverse relationship between capital structure and financial performance. Debt maturity has little impact on the relationship between capital structure and financial performance. However, the industry has an impact on the direction of the relationship between capital structure and financial performance. Debt maturity also has an impact on the correlation between capital structure performance and specific industries, but not for the market. This study expands on prior work by include institutional and sectorial investors. This study extends previous investigations into the relationship between capital structure and financial performance by using sector-specific data as well as information on the debt maturity of businesses in Ghana and Nigeria. Finance managers will find it simpler to maximize performance by considering financially justifiable heterogeneities such as the sector and the funding source.

Sorana, (2015) examined the impact of Capital structure on Financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria has a population of ten (10) firms quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December 2018 out of which ten (10) firms were selected as samples for a period of seven (7) years from 2012 to 2018 based on purposeful sampling technique. The study uses multiple regressions as a tool for analysis. The study reveals that short term debt, long term debt and Debt equity showed a positive significant impact on Financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that Short term, long term debt and Debt equity influences Financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria exchange group and therefore recommends that listed firms should go for short term debt and long term debt as it improves financial performance.

Houshang, Suzan, Mustafa, Nawaz and Rezart, (2022) a similar study in Nigeria that looked at the impact of capital structure parameters on manufacturing business performance also found a link between the two. Data from an annualized panel for a sample of 15 listed companies from various sectoral classifications, from 1999 to 2018.

excluding financial companies because of the peculiarity of their capital structure and the stringent legislative constraints on their choice of financing. Non-financial businesses are the focus of this study. Measures of the firm's market and book values include capital structure.

Arthur, (2019) study conducted in Sri Lanka on the correlation between structure of capital and the performance in financial term with special reference to manufacturing firms from 2008 to 2012 equally revealed a negative relationship between leverage and return on equity. Variable of measurement are Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Assets (ROA). 30 listed manufacturing companies were chosen as the sample. Using SPSS, the data were examined, and hypotheses were tested using correlation and regression analysis. Outcome of the study showed an inverse link between leverage and return on equity. Furthermore, there was no connection between leverage and return on assets.

Cheng, (2019) study was conducted in Indonesia to determine the extent of capital structure on return on assets in a profitability on banking sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2017-2019. The findings of the results shows that ROA has a positive influence, which means that the greater the ROA, the higher the value of the company or the maximum because high profits will provide guarantees and good prospects for companies using information such as investors to invest in certain issuers. This is because high profits tend to be followed by a high rate of return (dividends) to be obtained by investors, and if the value of the company's shares in the market is high, of course it will have a good impact on the value of the company.

Gathara, Kilika and Maingi, (2019) investigation into the impact of Capital structure on Financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria, showed that short term debt, long term debt and Debt equity has a positive significant impact on Financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria. The population of the study consists of ten (10) firms quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December 2018 out of which ten (10) firms were selected as samples for a period of seven (7) years from 2012 to 2018 based on purposeful sampling technique. The study uses multiple regressions as a tool for analysis. The study concludes that Short term, long term debt and Debt equity influences Financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria and therefore recommends that Security and Exchange Commission should encourage selected quoted firms to go for short term debt and long term debt as it improves financial performance.

Methodology

Population of the study consists of 9 (Nine) listed *Telecommunication* companies on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31st December 2021 (NSE Fact Book, 2021). Sample size consists of 7 (seven) firms selected by using purposive sampling techniques. Attempt to ensure all companies' selected have been listed and have minimum of ten (10) year annual published account, made purposive sampling techniques appropriate. Companies delisted and those listed during the period of ten years were not considered for the study so as to have a balanced data. Data were sourced from annual report of sampled Telecommunication companies, which were available on the data base of the Nigeria Exchange Group. Thirty years of observations were covered by the study for the period, 2012–2021. Regression analyses method was utilized in analyzing the data sourced. At a 5% level of significance, the F-statistic was employed to evaluate each explanatory variable's impact on the criterion variables separately. F statistics was employed to examine the model's general acceptability and goodness-of-fit from a statistical standpoint, also at the 5% level of significance.

Model Development

This study's objective is to examine how capital structure affect financial performance of telecommunications companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. Two key variables are utilized to meet the study's goal. These factors are both independent and dependent. The capital structure is the independent variable, while the financial performance of Telecommunications companies registered on the Nigerian Exchange Group is the dependent variable.

Thus,

Model developed is as shown below:

$$Y = f(X)$$

Y = Dependent Variable- Financial Performance (FP)

X = Independent Variables-Capital Structure (CS)

$$Y = y_1, y_2$$

$$X = x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4$$

$$y_1 = \text{PBT}; y_2 = \text{ROA}; y_3$$

$$y_1 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)$$

$$Y = f(X)$$

Y = Dependent Variable-Financial Performance (FP)

X = Independent Variables-Capital Structure (CS)

$$Y = y_1, y_2$$

$$y_1 = \text{PBT}; y_2 = \text{ROA}$$

$$X = x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4$$

x_1 = Short term debt (STD)

x_2 = Long term debt (LTD)

x_3 = Equity (EQT)

x_4 = Total debt (TD)

y_1 = Profit before Tax (PBT)

y_2 = Return on Asset (ROA)

$$X = x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4$$

$$PBT = f(\text{STD, LTD, EQT, TD}) \quad \text{- equation 1}$$

$$ROA = f(\text{STD, LTD, EQT, TD}) \quad \text{- equation 2}$$

Model 1

$$PBT_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 STD_{it} + \beta_2 LTD_{it} + \beta_3 EQT_{it} + \beta_4 TD_{it} + \mu_i$$

Model 2

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 STD_{it} + \beta_2 LTD_{it} + \beta_3 EQT_{it} + \beta_4 TDT_{it} + \mu_i$$

Thus, in line with the ability to agency theory adopted for this study and prior studies, the models are specified and justified.

Table 1. Explanation and measurement of variables

Sign	Dependent Variable	Proposed measurement
PBT	Profit Before Taxation	Proxy by PBT disclosed in annual report Ojelabi, (2023), Olaoye & Oluwatoyin (2019).
ROA	Return on Assets	Ganiyu, Rodionova& Samuel et al. 2019 Oke&Fadaka, 2021, Abor 2005
Sign	Independent Variable	Proposed measurement
Corporate Taxation Variables		
EQT	Equity	Dawar, 2014; Salim&Yadav, 2012; & Samuel et al. 2019

STD	Short Term Debt	Olaoye, Akintola, Soetan and Olusola(2020), Abor, 2005
LTD	Long Term Debt	Olaoye, Akintola, Soetan and Olusola(2020), Abor, 2005
TLD	Total debt	Olaoye, Akintola, Soetan and Olusola(2020)

Researchers' 2023

Results and Presentation of Data

Descriptive Statistics

This is done to summarize the basic features of the data. The results of the descriptive statistics are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
PBT	64040	138517	-3278	621,546
ROA	-0.0044	0.2013	-0.86	0.72
STD	163292	334692	0	1,533,480
LTD	92003	233781	0	1087634
EQTY	510758	1202147	-1582	4,566,864
TLD	255300	513057	1	2,148,365

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2023

Interpretation

Table 1 shows the summary statistics of all the variables obtained from the sampled telecommunication companies for the period under review.

Test of Hypotheses

H_0 : Capital structure has no significant effect on profit before tax of quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

Table 2: Estimation Results for Model One

Sector	PROFIT BEFORE TAX			
Estimation Techniques	Fixed Regression with Driscoll standard errors -			
Dependent Variable:	Coeff.	Std. Err	T-Stat	Prob
Constant				
STD	22.91	24.86	0.09	0.92*
LTD	23.08	24.86	0.10	0.92*
EQTY	0.04	00.18	2.58	0.01*
TD	-22.81	24.86	-0.09	0.92*
Adjusted R ²	0.8034			
F-Stat/Wald Stat	Chi ² _(4, 65) =71.51 (0.0000)			
Hausman Test	Chi ² ₍₂₎ =23.66 (0.0000)			
Testparm/LM Test	Chi ² _(4,62) = 9.60(0.00)			
Heteroskedasticity Test	Chi ² ₍₇₎ = 5.50 (0.00)			

Serial Correlation Test	$F_{(1,6)} = 1.857(0.2219)$
Cross sectional Dep	$0.612 = (0.5406)$

Source: Researcher compilation, 2023

@Chosen Significant level

Post-Estimation Results Interpretation Model

Model 1 examined the impact of capital structure on the profitability (profit before tax) of Nigerian listed telecommunications companies. The Hausman test was utilized to identify which regression estimation method to apply. Among the pooled OLS, fixed effects, and random effects results reported in Table 2, Model 1 was the most appropriate. Based on the results of the test, which had a p-value of 0.000, which was less than the study's specified level of significance of 5%. Fixed effects was found to be the most appropriate estimator and null hypothesis was rejected. Although the Hausman test result indicated that Fixed effects were adequate, the Hausman test result was confirmed using Testparm since this test aids in choosing between Fixed effects and Pooled OLS regression as the proper model.

$$PBT = f(STD, LTD, EQT, TD) \quad 1$$

$$PBT_{it} = 22.91STD_{it} + 23.08LTD_{it} + 0.48EQT_{it} + -22.82TD_{it} + \mu_i$$

Table 2 showed regression output for model 1. Model 1 evaluated the effect of Capital Structure on Profit before Tax. The result showed that Short Term Debt (STD), Long Term Debt (LTD) and Equity (EQT) exerted a positive effect on Profit before tax on the quoted telecommunication in Nigeria, this is indicated by their coefficients $\beta_2STD_{it} = 22.91$, $\beta_3LTD_{it} = 23.08$; $\beta_4EQT_{it} = 0.48$ and $\beta_5TD_{it} = -22.82$. This result is consistent with our a priori expectation in the study as it was expected that capital structure will have positive effect on profitability (profit before tax) on quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

The adjusted R-square which measures the proportion of the changes in financial Performance Index as the result in changes in capital structure stood at 0.8034. This implies that 80.34% changes in profitability Index can be explained by changes in capital structure while the remaining 19.66 % were other factors not captured in the model.

The result revealed that at a level of significance 0.05, the F-statistics is 71.51, while the p-value of the F-statistics is 0.0000 which is lower than the adopted level of statistics.

Therefore, the study rejected the null hypothesis and concludes that Capital structure has significant effect on profitability (profit before tax) of quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Capital structure has no significant effect on return on asset of quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

Table 3: Estimation Results for Model Two

Sector	RETURN ON ASSET			
Estimation Techniques	Fixed Regression with Robust Std. Error			
Dependent Variable: ROA	Coeff	Std. Err	T-Stat	Prob
Constant	-0.23	0.25	-0.95	0.36*
STD	0.19	0.72	2.67	0.10*
LTD	0.19	0.72	2.67	0.10*
EQUITY	-5.59	5.65	-0.99	0.32*
TD	-0.19	0.72	-2.67	0.10*
Adjusted R ²	0.1543			
F-Stat/Wald Stat	F _(4, 65) = 4.15 (0.0047)			
Hausman Test	Chi ² ₍₂₎ = 23.66 (0.000)			
Testparm/LM Test	F _(4, 65) = 4.15(0.0047)			
Heteroskedasticity Test	chi ² ₍₇₎ = 279.68(0.000)			
Serial Correlation Test	F _(1, 6) = 0.209(0.6637)			
Cross sectional Dep	0.200, = (0.8413)			

Source: Researcher compilation, 2023

@Chosen Significant level of 5%

Interpretation Model 2

Model 3 examined the impact of capital structure on asset return. The results of the pooled OLS, fixed effects, and random effects shown in Table 3b were compared using the Hausman test to evaluate which approach was best for estimating the regression Model 2. The best suitable estimate was determined to be Fixed effects based on the test's outcome, which had a p-value of 0.049, or less than the study's specified level of significance of 5%.

Although, the Hausman test result revealed the appropriateness of Fixed effects; however, the confirmation of the result of the Hausman test was carried out using Testparm as this test helps to decide the appropriate model between the Fixed effects and Pooled OLS regression. The results of the Testparm test with *p-value* of 0.0047, which is less than the significance level of 5 percent; confirms the appropriateness of Fixed effects in estimating the model.

$$ROA = f(STD, LTD, EQTY, TD)$$

2

$$ROA_{it} = 0.19STD_{it} + 0.19LTD_{it} - 5.59EQTY_{it} - 0.19TD_{it} + \mu_i$$

Model 2 assessed the effect of capital structure on return on asset. The result showed that short term debt and long term debt had a positive effect on Return on Asset, this is indicated by its coefficient $STD = 0.19$, $LTD = 0.19$. This result is consistent with our a priori expectation. Although, Equity and Total Debt exerted a negative effect on Return on Asset of Telecommunication companies in Nigeria ($EQTY = -5.59$, $TD = -0.19$). This result is not consistent with our a priori expectation as it was expected that all independent variables to exert positive effect on Return on Asset on telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Capital structure has no significant effect on return on equity of quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

Table 4: Estimation Results for Model Three

Sector	RETURN ON EQUITY			
Estimation Techniques	Random-effects Regression with Driscoll Kraay standard errors			
Dependent Variable: EQTY	Coeff	Std. Err	T-Stat	Prob
Constant	0.88	0.18	0.48	0.63
STD	0.79	0.53	14.81	0.00 *
LTD	0.79	0.53	14.81	0.00*
EQY	-1.97	4.15	-0.47	0.63
TD	-0.79	0.53	-14.81	0.00*
Adjusted R ²	0.7620			
F-Stat/Wald Stat	F(4, 65) = 56.23 (0.000)			
Hausman Test	Chi ² (3) = 23.66 (0.0469)			
Testparm/LM Test	F(4, 65) = 56.23 (0.000)			
Heteroskedasticity Test	Chi ² (1) = 3303.19 (0.000)			
Serial Correlation Test	F(1,6) =2.155 (0.1924)			
Cross sectional Dep	0.170 (0.8650)			

Source: Researcher compilation, 2023

@Chosen Significant level of 5%

Post-Estimation Results

Interpretation Model

Model 4 assessed how Nigerian telecommunications companies' return on equity was affected by their capital structure. The Hausman test was used to determine which method of estimating regression Model 3 among the pooled OLS, fixed effects, and random effects results shown in Table 4 was most appropriate. The test's result, which had a p-value of 0.0469, which is greater than the study's chosen level of significance of 5%, showed that random effects was the best estimator given its null hypothesis, which claims that there is no presence, thus, the study rejected the null hypothesis.

$$ROE = f(STD, LTD, EQTY, TD)$$

$$ROE_{it} = 0.79 STD_{it} + 0.79 LTD_{it} - 1.97 EQTY_{it} - 0.79 TD_{it} + \mu_1 \quad 3.$$

H₀4: Capital structure has no significant effect on return on capital employed of quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

Table 5: Estimation Results for Model Four

Sector	RETURN ON CAPITAL EMPLOYED			
Estimation Techniques	Fixed Regression with Robust Std. Error			
Dependent Variable: TD	Coeff.	Std. Err	T-Stat	Prob
Constant				
STD	0.037	0.048	7.74	0.000
LTD	0.037	0.048	7.74	0.000
EQT	-1.35	3.75	-0.36	0.721
TD	-0.375	0.484	-7.74	0.000
Adjusted R ²	0.4523			
F-Stat	F((4, 65) = 15.24 (0.000)			

Hausman Test	Chi ² ₍₃₎ = 23.66 (0.0227)
Testparm/LM Test	Chi ² ₍₀₁₎ = 42.74(0.000)
Heteroskedasticity Test	Chi ² ₍₄₁₎ = 3508.40 (0.000)
Serial Correlation Test	F _(1,40) = 46.128 (0.000)
Cross sectional Dep	-0.820 (0.4121)

Source: Researcher compilation, 2023

@Chosen Significant level of 5%

Post-Estimation Results

Interpretation

The impact of capital structure on return on capital employed in Nigerian telecommunications companies is determined by Model 4. The outcomes of choosing the best method for estimating the regression of model 4 between pooled OLS, fixed effects, and random effects are shown in Table 4. The Hausman test's p-value was 0.0227, which is less than the study's 5% level of significance. This indicates that Fixed effects is the best estimator based on its null hypothesis, which claims that there is an unsystematic difference in the model coefficient; thus, the null hypothesis was rejected by the investigation. Regardless of the appropriateness of the fixed effect, the study used Testparm to test for confirmation of the Hausman test in order to choose the best model between the fixed effect and pooled OLS regression; *therefore, the study rejected the null hypothesis.*

Regression Equation Results (Model 4)

$$ROCE = f(\text{STD}, \text{LTD}, \text{EQTY}, \text{TD}) \quad 4$$

$$ROCE_{it} = 0.037\text{STD}_{it} + 0.037\text{LTD}_{it} - 1.35\text{EQTY}_{it} - 0.037\text{TD}_{it} + \mu_1$$

Table 4 showed regression output for model 4. Model 4 evaluated the effect of Capital Structure on Return on Capital Employed. The findings revealed a strong correlation between short- and long-term debt. Their coefficients, $2\text{STD}_{it} = 0.037$, and $3\text{LTD} = 0.037$, show this. This conclusion is consistent with our study's a priori anticipation that capital structure will have a favorable impact on Nigeria's Return on Capital Structure Index.

The adjusted R-square which measures the proportion of the changes in Return on Capital Employed as the result in changes in capital structure stood at 0.4523. This implies that 45.23% changes in Return on Capital Employed can be explained by changes in capital

structure while the remaining 54.77% were other factors not captured in the model.

Discussion of Findings

The regression results in model one investigated the effect of capital structure on profit before tax on quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria and discovered that capital structure as measured by short term debt, long debt, equity, and total debt had a joint significant effect on profit before tax on quoted telecommunication companies in Nigeria. This is based on the results of F-statistics that is 0.0001 which is lesser than 5% chosen level of significant. Despite the fact that the overall model is jointly significant, three of the capital structure attributes measured (short term debt, long term debt) regression results show significant but positive relationship with profit before tax when tested individually. While equity show a positive insignificant effects on profit before taxation. Also, total debt shows a negative and significant effects on profit before taxation.

Also, the regression results in model two investigated the effect of capital structure on performance (Return on Asset) of telecommunication firms in Nigeria and found out that capital structure measured by short term debt, long term debt, equity and total debt had joint significant effect on return on asset Index of telecommunication companies in Nigeria. However, the overall model is jointly significant as the F-statistics result shows 0.0047 which is lower than 5% chosen significant level. Short Term Debt (STD) and Long Term Debt (LTD) attributes regression results show a significant positive relationship with Return on Asset when tested in individually. While Equity (EQTY) and Total debt (TD) show negative and significant effects on return on asset index.

This result was in consonant with the results of prior study carried out in Malaysia on the impact of capital structure on financial performance of construction firms.

Conclusion and Recommendations

According to the study's findings, capital structure has a positive and significant effect on the financial performance of listed telecommunication companies in Nigerian. The study also revealed a positive and significant association short term fund and return on asset and profit before taxation of telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

In line with the results and findings obtained in each of the hypotheses, the following recommendations were made which might be useful to the management, investors and shareholders, the policy makers, the government, and other stakeholders;aa

1. When it comes to telecommunication companies who are looking to obtain financing for day to-day operations or working capital, short term financing should

be used. This is shown by the fact that short term debt is positively connected with financial performance considerably as in the study.

2. Also, finding from this study revealed that Long term debt have a positive relationship with Performance so when trying to raise finance or funds, telecommunication companies to finance new project or expansion of relatively long time, long term financing should be utilized. Result from the study depicts a positive significant link with financial success provides proof for this assertion.
3. Base on the outcome the study that shows a positive and significant relationship between long term debt, total debt, equity return on asset, telecommunication companies should ensure they balance the three sources of fund in other to operate at optimum level that maximize return of stakeholders.
4. The management of telecommunication companies should use long term financing to finance long term project and short term financing to finance project of relatively short term and not vice versa. This is to avoid fund mismatch.

References

- Abu-Rub N, (2012). Capital Structure and Firm Performance: Evidence from Palestine Stock Exchange. *Journal of Money, Investment and Banking*, 23(1) 109-117.
- Abbas. U, S. Aziz & S.Khan .(2018) How does Debt Financing Affect Financial Performance? A Study of Transport Companies listed in Pakistan. *Financial Performance of Non-Financial Firms Listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange, Kenya. Applied Economics and Finance Journal*. 5(4).
- Abdikadir (2015). Equity Financing and Financial Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Garissa County, Kenya.1(2), 1-62.
- Abdullah & T. Tursoy (2021). Capital structure and firm performance: evidence of Germany under IFRS adoption. *Review of Managerial Science*, 15(2),379-398.
- Achieng, W. Muturi & J. Wanjare. (2019) Effect of Equity Financing Options on 8(1), 47-62.
- Ahmad A.R, M. M. Ahmad & J. G El-Maude, (2016) Capital Structure and Firm Performance in the Nigerian Cement Industry. *Archives of Business Research*, 4(6), 30-44.
- Akinleye & L. O. Akomolafe (2019). Capital Structure and Profitability of Manufacturing Firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. *Information Management and Business Review*. 11(3).

- Andrew, P.S. Ademola & N. K Adetayo. (2021) Capital Structure and Corporate Performance: An Empirical Study of Selected Telecommunication Firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Entrepreneurship*, 6(3), 49-67.
- Arthur (2019). Effects of Capital Structure On Profitability of the Manufacturing Industry: Testing The Fixed and Random Effect Model On Selected Firms in Ghana. *Journal of Asian Business Strategy*, (9) 2, 204-219.
- Ayange, C.E Nwude, R.H Idamoyibo Hwerien, C.N Ufodiana & E. S Udo. (2021). Effect of Capital Structure on Firms Performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 9(1), 2021, 15-23.
- Basit, & Z. Hassan (2017). Impact of Capital Structure on Firms Performance: A Study on Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) Listed Firms in Pakistan. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*, 4(2) 118-135.
- Birru (2016). The Impact of Capital Structure on Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Ethiopia. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 16 (8), 43-52.
- Cheng (2019). Determinants of Capital Structure of Chinese Listed Companies. *Journal of Business Research*, 57(4), 1341-1351.
- Chung, H. Yang & J.H. Won (2018). Relationships between the Capabilities and export performance of Korean clothing and textiles SMEs and the moderating effects of export mode on these relationships. *Research Journal of Management*. Vol.11(23), 2018, 18-23.
- El-Maude, A.R. Ahmad & M. M. Ahmad (2016). Capital Structure and Firm Performance in the Nigerian Cement Industry. *Archives of Business Research*, 4(6), 30-44.
- Evbayiro-Osagie & I.B. Enadeghe (2022). Capital Structure and Performance of Non-Financial Firms in Sub-Saharan Africa. [International Journal of Finance Research](#). 3 (1), 334-350.
- Farah, I. Farrukh & N. Faizaan (2016). Financial Performance of Firms: Evidence from Pakistan Cement Industry. *Journal of Teaching and Education* 3(2), 82-92.
- Gong, L. Arugu & KI Dandago (2014). The Impact of Ownership Structure on the Financial Performance of Listed Insurance Firms in Nigeria. *Human Resource Management Academic Research Society*. 4(1), 409-416.
- Haron (2014). Capital structure inconclusiveness: evidence from Malaysia, Thailand and Singapore. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 10(1), 23-38.
- . Houshang, D. Suzan, R.R. Mustafa, N Nawaz & D. Rezart (2022). Impact of Capital Structure on Profitability: Panel Data Evidence of the Telecom Industry in the

- United State. *Journal of Economics and Finance, University of Bahrain*. 6(4), 1-19.
- Johnny & P E. Ayunku. (2019). An Empirical Analysis of Effect of Capital Structure on Firm Performance: Evidence from Microfinance Banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting*. 7 (.9), 30-44.
- Khazaaleh (2017). Capital Structure in the Airline Industry- An empirical study of determinants of capital structure. *European financial management*. (11) 1,51-69.
- Meshack, F., Owa E, Nwadiolor & C.O Chiedu (2022). Long Term Debt Financing and Firm Financial Performance in Nigerian Listed Firms. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(4), 52-62.
- Mirza, C. & Javed, A. (2013). Determinants of financial performance of a firm: Case of Pakistani stock market. *Journal of Economics and International Finance*. 5(2),43-52.
- Mouna, Y. Jianmu, S.H., Havidz, & H. Ali (2017) The impact of capital structure on Firms performance in Morocco. *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management*, 6(10),11-16.
- Muhammad, I Bujang & T. A Hakim (2019). Capital Structure and Financial Performance of Malaysian Construction Firms. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*.9 (12),2019,1306-1319.
- Musila (2015). The Relationship Between Equity Financing and Financial Performance of the Energy and Petroleum Companies Listed at The Nairobi Securities Exchange. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3,11- 25.
- Myers & N. S. Majluf. (1984) Corporate Financing and Investment Decisions: When Firms Have Information That Investors Do Not Have. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 13(2), 187-221.
- Narinder, B. Mahima (2019). The Effect of Capital Structure on Profitability: An Empirical Panel Data Study. *Jindal Journal of Business Research*. 8(1), 65–77.
- Nassar. (2021). The Impact of Capital Structure on Financial Firm Performance of Palestinian Listed Companies. [**International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting Finance and Management Sciences**](#) 5(8),56-61.
- Olusola, H.Mengze, E.C Muruako & P.C Agulefo Prosper Chinedum (2022). The Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance-Evidence from Large Companies in Hong Kong Stock Exchange. *Journal of Business and Management*. 4 (10), 2022,1332-1361.
- Ogieva & A. O Ogiemudia (2019). Capital Structure and Firm Performance in Nigeria: Is Pecking Order Theory Valid? *Journal of Corporate Governance* 4 (2), (13-26).
- Ogebe, O.J. Ogebe, & K. Alewi (2013)**. The Impact of Capital Structure on Firms' Performance in Nigeria. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. 21(2), 1-25.

- Orji, E.O. Nwadiakor & N. Agubata. (2021). Effect of Debt-Equity Financing on Firms Performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*. 7(3).
- Onyebuchi. (2020). Assessing the Importance of Firms Financial Management. *Banking and Accounting Issues*.56-64.
- Opoku-Asante, E. C.f Winful, M. Sharifzadeh, & M. Neubert (2022) .The Relationship Between Capital Structure and Financial Performance of Firms in Ghana and Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*.7(1),236-244.
- Owolabi, A. D Kolawole, O.I. Ogungbade &A. C Adekoya. (2021). Equity Financing Options and Financial Performance of Listed Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Archaeology of Egypt*.18(7),1730-1741.
- Patel, A Borde, M. Mistry & J. G. Purohit (2020). An Analysis of the Financial Performance of Selected Indian I.T Firms. *Financial Highlights of Infosys Ltd*. 17(2), 1022-1037.
- Saad, M. A. H Abdul -Ghani, S. Ahmad & S M. N. S. Salim (2020). Effects of Equity and Debt Financing on SME Performance in Malaysia. *Business performance continued to improve in the third quarter*, 1. (3), 66-74
- Sorana. (2015) The impact of capital structure on financial performance in Romanian listed companies. *Procedia Economics and Finance* 32 (15) 1314 – 1322.
- Vu, T. Le & T. Nguyen (2020) The impact of capital structure on the performance of construction companies: a study from Vietnam stock exchanges. *Journal of Accounting*, 6 (2), 169–176.
- Yinusa, A. Ismail, R.Yulia & L.S. Olawale (2019). Capital Structure and Firm Performance in Nigeria. *African Journal of Economic Review*,7(1).